

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMEZAH****FIRST NAME: ISAAC NEWTON****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used Microsoft 365 on Windows 10 Pro

List your 5-7 key concepts with a page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15–23)
2. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33–39)
4. Style Guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–42)
5. Latin abbreviations and expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 58–62)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing, commonly used in scholarly publications, is characterised by a formal style. This type of writing often includes essays, which serve as evidence-based responses to hypotheses (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

Clarity is essential in academic essays, as the structure and conveyed ideas must be precise, leaving no room for misunderstanding. Therefore, starting early and thoroughly planning the writing process is crucial. Early preparation allows for careful consideration of ideas and a clear definition of the question to ensure comprehensive answers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7–8).

Proper planning and applying key concepts are vital for producing a quality academic essay. These concepts include correct punctuation, choosing between British or American English, avoiding colloquial language, following a style guide, and accurately using Latin abbreviations and expressions. I will now proceed to discuss each of these concepts in detail.

2) PUNCTUATIONS

I discovered how punctuation is invaluable for improving the clarity and professionalism of academic writing. I learnt that punctuations provide clear rules that help students avoid common errors that can detract from their work's readability and credibility. I found out that mastery of punctuation is fundamental to effective communication. Proper punctuation ensures that sentences are unambiguous, which is essential in academic writing where precision is paramount. It also helps establish a professional tone, enhancing the writer's credibility (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 22).

I have, however, learned that the general rule for punctuation is that one must use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the sentence's meaning. My discovery was the use of ellipses. This is because I have hardly used it. I learnt that ellipses are primarily used in the context of quotations and academic writing. I noted that ellipse indicates the omission of words in a quoted passage. They are placed within the middle of a quote to omit unnecessary words without changing the meaning and to ensure that the omission does not alter the original meaning of the quoted text (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 22–23).

3) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I prefer British English to American English because it is the official language of communication in my home country, Ghana. However, there have been several occasions where I have combined both American and British English in my writing, even though I recognise that American English spellings are also correct and can be visually appealing. For instance, American English often uses simpler spelling forms, such as “color,” “honor,” and “theater”, while British English uses more complex forms like “colour,” “honour,” and “theatre” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25–26).

I also noted the differences in grammar and usage; for instance, in terms of Past Tense Forms, American English often uses “gotten” as the past participle of “get.”, while British English typically uses “got.” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25–27).

In all of this, I have generally followed the British writing style, though only sometimes consistently. I have learnt the importance of consistently using a particular English language style throughout an academic paper to maintain clarity and professionalism. These differences are crucial for understanding and applying them correctly in my academic work.

4) PLAGIARISM

In academic practice, reading and reviewing other scholarly materials is highly encouraged. The practice, however, is that you acknowledge the sources of information,

ideas, data, and quotes used in your work. Once this source of information is not recognised, one may be involved in plagiarism.

Plagiarism occurs when a writer intentionally uses another person's language, ideas, or original material without giving proper credit to the source (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). This behaviour constitutes academic dishonesty.

I noted that citations credit the original authors of the ideas or words you are using through in-text citations, footnotes, or endnotes, as well as in the bibliography. Even if a piece of information is paraphrased, it is just ethical to give credit to the source (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35–36). I learnt that in an event where a statement is used verbatim, there is the need to use quotation marks to indicate direct quotes from a source by ensuring that the quoted text is the same as it appears in the source (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 36).

It will be tough to say that I can write any scholarly essay without paraphrasing, copying, and pasting or relying on other materials that will be relevant to my course. I learnt that consistency is critical in citations. I agree with the authors that a consistent citation style throughout your work is essential. For this assignment, the in-text rule enjoins me to do citations within the actual text itself. I must strive to contribute my analysis, insights, and ideas to my academic work and use sources to support my arguments.

Finally, it is essential for me to avoid plagiarism and maintain intellectual integrity, which is crucial for my academic and professional credibility.

5) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide in academic writing ensures document consistency, clarity, and professionalism. It includes rules on formatting, such as font type and size, line spacing, text alignment, and guidelines for organising content with appropriate headings (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41).

I learnt the importance of proper citation and referencing, detailing how to cite sources within the text and compiling a comprehensive bibliography or reference list using styles like APA, MLA, or Chicago. I took notice of the usage of language and grammar, which guides how to maintain an academic tone and correct punctuation. Additionally, it is very instructive to quote and paraphrase sources to avoid plagiarism accurately.

Adhering to these guidelines will assist me in producing clear, organised, and credible academic work.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

I found it interesting when I was reading about Latin abbreviations and expressions. I have used some of these expressions several times and have yet to learn their original

origin and meanings. Reading through this subject matter has provided me with a better understanding of their usage.

As I understand it, these Latin abbreviations are frequently used in academic writing and various professional fields to convey complex ideas concisely. For example, “e.g.” (exempli gratia), meaning “for example,” is used to provide examples in a sentence. Similarly, “i.e.” (id est), meaning “that is” or “in other words,” is used to clarify or restate something differently (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 59–61).

I identified that while Latin abbreviation is acceptable in footnotes, bibliographies, and casual writing, it is not suited for official writing. I learnt that to prevent confusing the reader, always avoid using Latin expressions but rather always choose the English equivalent.

I appreciate that understanding and correctly using these Latin abbreviations and expressions can enhance clarity, precision, and professionalism in academic and professional writing as they provide a succinct way to present complex information and demonstrate familiarity with scholarly conventions.

7) CONCLUSION

In academic writing, clarity and professionalism are paramount. Proper punctuation is crucial for unambiguous communication. Choosing between American and British English should be consistent with maintaining readability and professionalism. Avoiding plagiarism by correctly acknowledging sources through citations is essential to uphold academic integrity. Following a style guide ensures consistency and clarity in formatting and language use, enhancing the overall quality of the work. Additionally, appropriately understanding and using Latin abbreviations can further refine academic writing, contributing to its precision and professionalism. Adhering to these principles will enable the production of credible, well-structured, and effective academic essays.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.